

Quantum communications between micro-organisms and macro-systems through electrons, photons and spinning micro-bubbles

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Abstract: Micro-organisms show many quantum effects and usually exchange information with each other through quantum particles like electrons, photons and some micro-bubbles with $\frac{1}{2}, 1, \dots$ spins. We can summarize some of these quantum effects as 1. DNAs, membranes, emitted ions and other elements of microbes are formed from charged particles and by their motions, some quantum waves are emerged. Some of these structures show quantum spinning behavior and could interact with other spinors. These micro-organisms and their emitted charges and gases may be confined by water molecules and form some quantum spinning micro-bubbles. These micro-organisms and also their related micro-bubbles could interact with some external magnetic fields like earth's one and their spins become parallel or anti-parallel respect to them. 2. DNAs, membranes and charges around micro-organisms or within the micro-bubbles could absorb photons of a light source, excited and produce new photons with different frequencies. This causes to the emergence of rainbow colors around microbes or micro-bubbles. These colors could be used in diagnosing type of microbe or micro-bubble specially in conditions that chemical coloring cause to missing many facts about evolutions of system. 3. By using multi-gonal lamps as the light source, one can induce several photonic lines in micro-bubbles around the microbes and control their behaviors. It is interesting that micro-bubbles take the shape of macro-light source and microbes within them interact with each photonic line separately. 4. In addition to micro-bubbles, micro-organisms could build some biological colonies which their shapes are similar to the multi-gonal light source. 5. It seems that microbes under lenses of microscope see the macro-objects in their size. This means that as lenses of microscopes produce big images of microbes for us from one side, make some small images of macro-objects in the scale of microbes from other side. Microbes usually have some sensors or gates in their membranes which

absorb photons and feel any change in light. For example, if one put a macro-object on the eye-lens, photons of light source pass the lenses, collide with it and return to microbes. Then, microbes feel this change and interact with shadow or image of that object. 6. Some micro-organisms like chloroplasts or cyanobacteria have electronic transport and exchange some ions and charges with medium. If one put two parts of a leaf on the metal with a separation distance from each other, chloroplasts shoot electrons and ions. These ions act like some spinors, are surrounded by water molecules and form some micro-bubbles. These spinning micro-bubbles interact with each other and form some biological lines which are strength from one part of a leaf to another one. 7. Sometimes, some microbes also interact with chloroplasts and exchange ions and electrons with them. These microbes also maybe form micro-bubbles, join to each other and produce biological lines. 8. Water memory could be also used as a quantum method in communicating between cells. A dirty water which was near some cells like plant ones or blood cells, store their electronic properties like ions, charges and photons even after removing cells. This water could produce some micro-bubbles which transform these properties to some target cells within the clean water.

Keywords: Quantum mechanics; Micro-Organisms; Electrons; Photons; MiCRO-Bubbles; Leaf; Chloroplast; Transport

I. Introduction

Up to date, it has been known that micro-organisms like bacteria show some quantum effects and use of quantum channels for exchanging information with each other and medium. Some of them like magnetotactic bacteria, caple bacteria, photosynthetic bacteria, luminous bacteria and exoelectrogenic bacteria have special structures and could emit or absorb quantum particles like photons and electrons. Some others have no special antenna; however, their structures are formed from charged particles and consequently, by motions of these charges, some currents are emerged. These currents could exchange waves with any external biological and non-biological currents. Among bacteria with special structures; we can refer to magnetotactic bacteria which could exchange quantum electromagnetic waves with medium. Magnetotactic bacteria (or MTB) are a polyphyletic group of bacteria that orient themselves along the magnetic field

lines of Earth's magnetic field and also other magnetic fields[1]. Magnetotactic bacteria (MTB) have the unique ability to produce magnetic particles surrounded by a biomembrane to form the magnetosome organelle. Therefore, MTB have novel physical and magnetic properties and have consequently been used in several biotechnological applications. For example, they could be used to generate electricity based on Faraday's law of electromagnetic induction [2]. Another example is the cable bacteria which conduct electricity across distances over 1 cm in sediment and groundwater aquifers and connect electron donors to electron acceptors [3]. In addition to these two groups, there is a third group of photosynthetic bacteria like purple [4] and Cyanobacteria [5,6] that are phototrophic, capable of producing their own food and energy via photosynthesis. Furthermore, Bioluminescent bacteria are another type of bacteria which produce light. These bacteria are predominantly present in sea water, marine sediments, the surface of decomposing fish and in the gut of marine animals [7]. And finally, exoelectrogenic bacteria are another main micro-organisms which have the ability to transfer electrons extracellularly [8]. Besides these special bacteria, normal bacteria also exchange quantum particles with medium. For example, some authors have disclosed that 460–470 nm light-emitting diode could inhibit the growth of some bacteria like *E. coli*. Their study has shown that bacterial growth inhibition by LED was more effective at 4 °C than at 25 °C [9]. In another work, researchers have reported effects of light-dark cycles on photosynthetic bacteria wastewater treatment and valuable substances production. Their results have asserted that 24 h light/24 h dark cycle led the best biomass production and 3h light/3h dark cycle led the highest protein [10]. In another investigation, it has been demonstrated that exposing *L. acidophilus* and *L. Casei* probiotic bacteria to radiofrequency electromagnetic radiation (RF-EMF) of Wi-Fi router show significantly increased proliferation and lactic acid production [11].

Until now, only, the role of quantum mechanics in evolutions of bacteria has been considered. However, there are other biological objects like chloroplasts and microbubbles which of quantum particles for exchanging information with medium. Chloroplasts which play the main role in photosynthesis, could absorb quantum photons from medium and send quantum charges like H^+ , electrons and other particles to extracellular space [12]. On the other hand, micro-bubbles are

biological objects which are formed from water molecules, gases and charged ions and can be formed around micro-organisms like bacteria and viruses. These micro-bubbles could be collapsed by ultrasound waves and some quantum photons are produced. These photons may play the main role in destruction/growth or any other evolutions of micro-organisms like bacteria [13,14]. Motived by these researches, we propose some experimental methods to consider the exvchanged quantum particles between micro-organisms, micro-bubbles and cells.

II. Material and method

A. Material

Materials in this research are

1. Light microscope
2. Plant cells
3. Light sources with different shapes
4. Some metals like iron
5. Some colonies of microbes

B. Method:

1. Biological objects like DNAs within cells and microbes are formed from charged particles and by their motions, some electromagnetic waves are emerged. Sometimes, these objects show quantum effects like spin and form biological spinors. These spinors could be surrounded by molecules and build some micro-bubbles. These micro-bubbles including spins interact with magnetic field of earth and other magnetic fields and will be parallel or anti-parallel to it. Consequently, some biological lines could be observed along the external magnetic fields (See figure 1).

2. Some of micro-bubbles are formed around micro-organisms like bacteria. These microbes emit or absorb some charges like electrons and ions. Type of absorbed/emitted charges and their velocity are different from a bacteria or microbe to another. Consequently, micro-tubes which are emerged around these microbes depend on the genus and biological properties of them. When, we close a light source to these micro-bubbles, ions around them and also membranes of microbes absorb photons and emit new photons with different frequencies. Thus, we could observe rainbow colors around the micro-bubbles which are different for each type of microbes (See figure 2).

3. To observe the quantum effects on the micro-bubbles, we could use of multi-gonal light source (See Figure 3). It is interesting that each micro-bubbles takes shape of light source and emits multi-gonal photonic shapes (See figure 4).

4. To observe the mico-organisms, we usually use of a microscope. This is because that its lenses make the microbes bigger and produce some images in our scale. However, the same occurs for microbes. Lenses of microscope make the small image of us and other macro-objects in the scale of microbes. If we put an object on the above eye lens, some of photons which are emitted from light source and pass the lenses, confront this object and return to microbes. Thus, microbes could feel a change in the light of source and notice the existence of a new object. However, they see this object in their scales. The process of seeing in microbes may be different from us and probability, they use of some special gates in their membranes for absorbing or detecting photons. Some of them, like photosynthetic bacteria use of photons in building food and energy. In any case, microbes could diagnose macro-objects in their scale (See figure 5).

5. One of micro-organisms which may help us to understand the role of quantum mechanism in biological process could be chloroplasts and plant cells. Chloroplasts within the plant cells take photons, form some electronic chains and emit some ions like H^+ . Some of these electrons and ions escape from chloroplasts and plant cells, surrounded by water molecules and produce micro-bubbles. These micro-bubbles including spinors could move along a metal and interact with micro-bubbles with opposite spins from other chloroplasts. These microbubbles join to each other and form the biological lines or wires (See figure 7)

Fig 1. Formation of microbubbles from biological spinors and interaction with magnetic field of the earth

Fig 2: Emergence of micro-bubbles with different colors around microbes

Fig 3: A light source which could be used for inducing different shapes on the water bubbles

Fig 4: Induction of the shape of source into micro-bubbles

Fig 5: Microbes diagnose **macro**-organisms and objects

Fig 6: Chloroplasts act like quantum weapons and exchange charges with each other.

Fig 7. Formation of micro-bubbles including spinors within the dirty water and shooting towards chloroplasts, plant cells and other types of biological system

III. Results

1. In figure 8 and 9, we show the normal life of micro-organisms near the plant cells under a light microscope. Usually, microbes interact with each other and exchange some charges and ions (See figure 8). To exchange quantum particles with plant cells, microbes like to build some lines along the plant cell walls or near the membrane gates (See figure 9). Also, some microbes become close to chloroplasts and exchange waves and quantum charges with them.
2. If we change light source and close a small lamp to micro-organisms, some of them form micro-bubbles with rainbow colors (See figure 10). Each of these colors introduce a special interaction between photons and ions or charges around or within the micro-organisms.
3. When, the light source is distant from system, a plant cell shoot some micro-bubbles including ions and micro-organisms and produce some biological lines (See figure 11). By closing lamp, some micro-bubbles show rainbow colors which are signatures of interaction between photons and ions or charges around micro-organisms (See figure 12).
4. Some of micro-bubbles include only ions or charges. They could interact with external magnetic field and oscillate in their places. However, some micro-bubbles include micro-organisms. These micro-bubbles move towards

special target and interact with each other and external fields (See figures 13 and 14).

5. To observe photonic effects, we can change light source and use of a multi-gonal lamp. It is observed that all micro-bubbles take shape of this new light source. It is wonderful that lightsource is a macro-object, while micro-bubbles see it in their scale and absorb/emit its waves (See figure 15). We press the objective lenses on the slide to see micro-organisms within the micro-bubbles. It seems that micro-organisms interact with each part of multi-gonal lamp separately (See figures 16-19).
6. Near a multi-gonal lamp, micro-organisms specially those who live on a metal, build multi-gonal colonies (See figures 20 and 21). In addition to micro-organisms, micro-bubbles also follow of the light source and produce multi-gonal shapes (See figure 22) .
7. Lenses of microscope not only produce some big images of micro-organisms for us, but could act reversely and build some small images of macro-objects for microbes. Micro-organisms have their own sensors for taking light and could notice any change in the light. For example, if we put some objects on the eye lens, we can observe some actions of microbes which show they notice these changes (See figures 23-25) .
8. In addition to photonic transport, electronic transport is another quantum effect which could be seen in biological systems. Chloroplasts of plant cells shoot some ions and electrons. These charges are surrounded by water molecules and form micro-bubbles. These bubbles join to each other and form biological lines. These lines could be emerged and seen between two parts of a leaf which are located on a metal (See figures 26-33). The genus of metal is very main, because it helps that electronic transport is done better (See figures 34-36). In addition to metal, light source is another main parameter. For example, a multi-gonal lamp induces multi-gonal micro-bubbles within the biological lines and change some electronic properties of information teleporting between cells (See figure 37). And finally, if we close a magnet to the metal, we could change the shape of biological lines between cells and produce some regions (See figure 38). In each region, seems that direction of spinors within the micro-bubbles is different respect to other region.

9. Water memory is another quantum aspect of biological systems. If a liquid be near the cells like plant cells, micro-organisms or blood ones and then close it to pure water, some microbubbles are formed in the boundary of two liquids and shoot towards cells within clean water. It is because that by removing cells from dirty water, some electronic properties of cells like their emitted charges, ions and photons remain in dirty water and could be teleported to other cells in a clean water (See figures 39 and 40).

Fig 8. A natural life of micro-organisms near the plant cells

Fig 9: A natural life of microbes near the cell walls of a plant leaf

Fig 10: Formation of micro-bubbles with different colors around ions and micro-organisms by changing the light source

Fig 11: Shooting microbes and ions by plant cells in a non-normal light

Fig 12: Induction of rainbow colors into micro-bubbles around ions and micro-organisms by closing a light source

Fig 13: Formation of micro-bubbles with different colors around ions and micro-organisms

Fig 14: Interaction between micro-bubbles which are formed around ions and micro-organisms

Fig 15: Induction of image of light source into micro-bubbles

Fig 16: Micro-organisms within the micro-bubbles (First picture)

Fig 17: Micro-organisms within the micro-bubbles (Second picture)

Fig 18: Micro-organisms within the micro-bubbles (Third picture)

Fig 19: Micro-organisms within the micro-bubbles (Forth picture)

Fig 20. Bulding multi-gonal colonies of microbes and micro-bubbles by a multi-gonal source (First picture)

Fig 21. Bulding multi-gonal colonies of microbes and micro-bubbles by a multi-gonal source (Second picture)

Fig 22. Bulding multi-gonal colonies of fatty/oil/water micro-bubbles by a multi-gonal source

Fig 23: Interacting micro-organisms and micro-bubbles with macro-objects (First picture)

Fig 24: Interacting micro-organisms and micro-bubbles with macro-objects
(Second picture)

Fig 25: Interacting micro-organisms and micro-bubbles with macro-objects (Third picture)

Fig 26: Shooting micro-bubbles and micro-organism and formation of biological lines by plant cells (First picture)

Fig 27: Shooting micro-bubbles and micro-organism and formation of biological lines by plant cells (Second picture)

Fig 28: Shooting micro-bubbles and micro-organism and formation of biological lines by plant cells (Third picture)

Fig 29: Shooting micro-bubbles and micro-organism and formation of biological lines by plant cells (Forth picture)

Fig 30: Shooting micro-bubbles and micro-organism and formation of biological lines by plant cells (Fifth picture)

Fig 31: Shooting micro-bubbles and micro-organism and formation of biological lines by plant cells (Sixth picture)

Fig 32: Shooting micro-bubbles and micro-organism and formation of biological lines by plant cells (seventh picture)

Fig 33: Shooting micro-bubbles and micro-organism and formation of biological lines by plant cells (eighth picture)

Fig 34: Formation of biological lines by the help of metal and leaves

Fig 35: Formation of biological lines by the help of metal and leaves (Second picture)

Fig 36: Formation of biological lines by the help of metal and leaves (Third picture)

Fig 37: Formation of biological lines from multi-gonal micro-bubbles by the help of metal, light sources and leaves

Fig 38. Formation of different regions of biological lines by the help of metals, magnets and leaves

Fig 39. Formation of biological line in the boundary of a liquid with memory of cells and microbes and normal water

Fig 40. Shooting micro-bubbles from liquid with memory of cells and microbes towards plant cells.

Conclusions:

In this research, we have shown that micro-organisms could have quantum information teleporting with each other and macro-systems. They have built from quantum charges and by each motion of these charges, some waves are emerged. Also, some of them have spins and play the role of spinors. These microbes and their emitted charges or ions could be surrounded by water molecules and form

spinning micro-bubbles. These bubbles could interact with external magnetic fields and produce some biological lines. Also, ions and charges within these micro-bubbles could absorb photons, excited and emit new photons which cause to formation of some rainbow colors around them. These colors may act as inducer of microbes or ions and be used instead of chemical colors. On the other hand, using multi-gonal lamps, one can force to micro-bubbles and microbes to produce multi-gonal shape colonies. Also, by using lenses of microscope, one can induce small images of some macro-objects which could be seen by microbes and cause to their related action. In addition to photonic properties, charge transport is another property of microbes. For example, one can put two parts of a leaf near each other on a metal. Chloroplasts in each part shoot electrons and ions which are taken by microbes or confined within micro-bubbles. These microbes and micro-bubbles form biological lines between two parts. Finally, water memory is one of the main results of quantum mechanics which could be used in communicating between cells. A dirty water which was included micro-organisms and cells, even after removing these objects, retain their electronic properties. When this water become close to a clean water including other cells, some micro-bubbles are formed and shoot from dirty water towards target cells.

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